

ENTREPRENEURSHIP TEACHING METHODS, MODERATED BY ENVIRONMENTAL ECOSYSTEM IN INCULCATING ENTREPRENEURIAL PROPENSITY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN KENYA

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Abstract: This study investigated how entrepreneurship teaching methods influence the development of entrepreneurial propensity among university students in Kenya. Driven by global trends such as market shifts, technological evolution, and globalization, the study recognizes the emergence of entrepreneurial opportunities amidst market imperfections. Guided by the human capital theory and a realism philosophical approach, a mixed method design was adopted. The target population consisted of fourth-year university students, with data collected through simple random sampling using self-administered semi-structured questionnaires. Both primary and secondary data were analyzed using quantitative and qualitative methods with SPSS software. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between entrepreneurship teaching methods and entrepreneurial propensity. Consequently, the study recommends a review of current teaching methods and the entrepreneurship curriculum to enhance practicality and experiential learning. A notable gap identified is the absence of follow-up to determine whether students inclined toward entrepreneurship eventually became entrepreneurs—suggesting an area for future research.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Teaching Methods, Entrepreneurial Propensity, University Students, Curriculum Development, Kenya.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The concept of who an entrepreneur is and what is entrepreneurship has existed since the 16th century. The word entrepreneur was used to refer to those people who engaged in military expeditions in the early 16th century (Khanka, 2000). In the 17th, the term entrepreneur was used to refer to civil engineers who were engaged in construction activities. It was not until the 18th century that the word entrepreneur was viewed from an economic point (Khanka, 2000). It is believed that Richard Cantillon was the first person to use the word entrepreneur. From His point of view, an entrepreneur was a risk taker, an individual who bought goods at a certain price to later resell them at uncertain price hence operating at a risk (Khanka, 2000).

Shigeru Fijii is the person who pioneered the concept of entrepreneurship education. It was first taught at Kobe University in Japan in 1938 (Fayolle, 2009). For entrepreneurship education to be effective, it should aim at fostering entrepreneurial attitudes, skills and a mindset that covers a wide range of aspects that would include the generation of business ideas, how to start business and enhance economic growth and innovation (Fayolle, 2009). In the mid-1940s and 1949 courses in small

business management began to emerge. It was first started by Myles Mace in USA at Harvard Business School (Fayolle, 2009). Half a century later the phenomenon gained more universal recognition (Alberti, 2004).

Currently, entrepreneurship is taught at nearly every American Assembly of College Schools of Business (AACSB) and other accredited institution. It is taught in over 1400 post-secondary schools in the United States of America. (Honing, 2004). Despite the growth in the number of universities offering entrepreneurship courses, different opinions still abound on whether entrepreneurship can be taught or not. The question on whether entrepreneurs are born or made still fills discussions in international journals as well as in conferences held all over the world.

This argument can as well be adopted for entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs and still hold water (Hindel, 2004). Teaching entrepreneurship can be viewed as both art and a science (Jack & Anderson, 1998). It is considered a science because it relates to the functional skills which are basically required for business start-up (it is this part of entrepreneurship that appears to be teachable). Entrepreneurship education covers a wide variety of objectives, contents as well as pedagogical methods (Fayolle, 2008).

In general, entrepreneurship education may be viewed as a discipline that increases awareness of entrepreneurship as a career option, consequently enhancing the understanding of the process that is involved in initiating and managing new business venture (Lee, 2004).

Undergraduates' students in Kenyan Universities

Employability of University graduates as well as their ability to start new ventures them enable them employ other Kenyans and at the same time contribute to the Countries economic well being is quite important to the mission of the University education system in Kenya. There is sufficient support that reveals that University students can be used as appropriate subjects in research on entrepreneurial propensity and behavior (Khera & Benson, 1970, Krueger, Rally and Carsrud, 2000) thus; they are well positioned for the purpose of this study. The Government sponsored students through the public universities and the Joint admission Board (JAB) and those in self-sponsored programme (SSP) are considered important in this study for various reasons.

Statement of the Problem

It is important that young people are integrated in the labor market upon graduation so

that the many negative consequence of graduates' unemployment is reduced as much as possible. Young people in Kenya account for more than 35 % of the total national population, of which 67% are the country's unemployed workforce (Otieno, 2016). 1-2 graduates are still unemployed and only 1 in every 5 youth with university degrees are self-employed. Both public and private universities in Kenya churned out about 50,000 graduates every year. This number continues to pile into the number of the youths in Kenya who are unemployed estimated to be approximately 2.3 million (RoK, 2016). The introduction of entrepreneurship education in Kenya in 2005 was to address the issue of unemployment.

The Government of Kenya viewed entrepreneurship education as a tool that can be used to address the unemployment problem, nevertheless, the problem seems to be escalating (Otieno, 2016). This results to the many problems that come as a result of unemployment such as, increased poverty rates, deskilling, social exclusion, and lack of motivation as well as mental health problems. It is due to lack of employment fresh graduates often find themselves trapped in a vicious cycle.

An increased level of graduate unemployment has a negative effect on the economic growth as well as the productivity of a Nation. Kenya for instance is at a risk of losing talent and skills. This is because a great number of university graduates are unemployed and therefore, they cannot put their knowledge and capabilities into producing innovation and contributing to the country's economic growth. A large number of unemployed workforce leads to reduced productivity and less gross domestic product (GDP) (World Bank, 2015). As a result, the country gets less in form of GNP which can only be improved if more people are working hence contributing to the general economic growth of a Nation. Mkala & Wanjau (2013) researched on transforming implementation of entrepreneurship education programme in technical training institutions in Kenya. Ngugi, Gakure, Waithaka & Kiwara (2012) conducted a study on the application of shapero's model in explaining entrepreneurial intentions among university students in Kenya.

General Objective

The purpose of this study was to establish the relationship between entrepreneurship education and environmental dynamism in inculcating entrepreneurial propensity among entrepreneurship students in Kenyan Universities.

Specific Objectives

To determine the relationship between entrepreneurship teaching methods and entrepreneurial propensity among entrepreneurship University students in Kenya.

Hypotheses

Based on the specific research objectives, the study examined the following null hypothesis

H01: There is no relationship between entrepreneurship teaching methods and entrepreneurial propensity among university entrepreneurship students in Kenya

Justification of the Study

Kenyan economy can greatly benefit from the 50,000 graduates who are churned out of the University every year. Studies reveal that economic development of any Country is made possible by proper utilization of its human capital. Having been through a formal learning, it means such students would perform businesses differently from ordinary people, would be more creative and even apply tools such as business plan to ensure business success. If Kenya is to achieve its well stipulated Vision 2030, then proper utilization of entrepreneurship students in job creation are of paramount importance

Significance of the Study

The findings in this study will greatly benefit the students pursuing entrepreneurship course. It may be a wake-up call in helping them question their preparedness in self employment upon graduation. Students will see the need to be well prepared in creating jobs as opposed to seeking job upon completion of their studies. The study is also important in enabling the government to understand whether the long-sought solution of unemployment is being addressed by entrepreneurship education in the higher institutions of learning in Kenya. The policy makers might consider reviewing the policy already implemented on entrepreneurship Education. The curriculum developers may also benefit from this research findings as it may enable them review the current entrepreneurship curriculum. The world of academicians can benefit from the findings of this research as the lecturers might want to review their teaching methods and strengthen their social net works. The universities would also benefit from the findings in this study from the recognition that the ecosystems play a role in achieving the long-sought objective of inculcating entrepreneurial propensity among entrepreneurship students. The study has left gaps for further research

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

Environmental Dynamism Concept

Environmental dynamism is the frequent changes that occur in the environment. Wijbenga and Van Witteloostuign (2007), it is the rate at which the preference of customers and the services of organisations change over time. An act of entrepreneurship can ameliorate a constraint rather than being limited by it Rammel, (2003). One of the ways in which this can be attained is by shifting resources, substituting resources. This would include adopting new technologies changing business models in order to bear on the problems. It may also include coming up with new forms of contracts in organization Rammel, (2003). Environmental constraint can be a function of an incentive within which entrepreneurial agents can see business opportunities.

A study by Zapalska (2003) revealed that various environmental factors affected entrepreneurs of New Zealand. Ullah (2011) in his study he emphasized that both environmental dynamism and environmental heterogeneity are significant predictors of entrepreneurial orientation and that it has a positive effect on entrepreneurial propensity. Jalali (2012), in his study, he found that environmental determinants affected risk taking and innovativeness which are considered as basic dimensions of entrepreneurial propensity. Gul (2011) affirms that environmental dynamism has a positive effect on firm performance.

Economic evolution that is associated with creative destruction dominates the slow evolutionary dynamics of the ecosystem which consequently weakens its resilience (Gual and Norgaard 2010). Metcalfe (1998) confirms that the knowledge base of the economic order is ever changing rapidly. Environmental dynamisms capabilities influence how new ventures are created and shape its resource position and capabilities which affect the new business performance (Zott 2003). Jantunen (2005) analyzed the relationship between entrepreneurial propensity and internationalized performance. The findings revealed that environmental dynamics has a great effect on international firm performance (Jantunen, 2005). Environmental dynamisms are helpful to leverage entrepreneurial resources to benefit start-up businesses (Wu, 2007). A study by Teece (2007) revealed that new ventures rely on environmental sensing capabilities and response capabilities so that they may dynamically adapt to a new complicated environment. New ventures achieve knowledge from the environment, configure it and integrate its operational capabilities at the end of it they internally change and effectively respond to new market demand and consequently realize the dynamic match between internal resources and external environment.

Entrepreneurship Education Concept

The need for a person anticipating to become an entrepreneur in future as a result of skills acquisition cannot be over emphasized (Ibrahim & Lucky, 2014). In general, entrepreneurship has become a major concern to both scholars and policy makers. This is due to the understanding of the significant role it plays in economic and social growth (Brsncu, 2015). Entrepreneurship education has been considered as the avenue responsible in driving innovation, creates employment and is also essential for economic transformation and advancement (Hathaway & Litan, 2014). Many governments have considered entrepreneurship as a panacea that facilitates economic growth and especially in Counties that are still developing (Thornton, 2011). Kenya being a developing Country has developed policies that encourage self-reliance after students graduate from the universities; consequently, it has made entrepreneurship studies compulsory to students, even those not taking business courses (Akambi, 2013). The possibility of entrepreneurial trained students to become entrepreneurs in future has continuously been a challenge to the government and to the scholars as well (Abidin & Bakar, 2005; Lucky & Maina, 2011). Many students still have their eyes on white collar jobs and are still adamant on taking entrepreneurship as a career option despite its numerous advantages (Akambi, 2013). This situation has lead to increased rate of unemployment and an increase in poverty rate (Olotu, 2015). It has become evident that entrepreneurship education does not only transform students to become venture creators but it has the ability to transform their propensity towards entrepreneurship (Taatila & Down, 2012). Entrepreneurship awareness has in the recent past touched almost every country in the world. This has been as a result of the increasing global competition that is based on creativity and innovation (Kelly, 2012). Past studies reveal the important role of entrepreneurship education with regard to creation of successful entrepreneurs particularly in Africa (Izedomni & okafor, 2010, Njoroge & Gatungu, 2013). Increased interest in entrepreneurship can as well be attributed to the changing structure of the western economy, the trend to downsize large companies, changing business patterns and the developing market economies such as China, India as well as Eastern Europe (Kelley, 2012). Ability to predict entrepreneurial characteristics draws attention to the significant role that entrepreneurship training and development plays including the mentorship and the grooming process in the early adulthood (Ibrahim & Ellis, 2002). It can therefore be concluded that the relative importance of education in enhancing entrepreneurial traits is very high. This can be supported by the fact that many associations allocate a great deal of resources to educate their members through external and internal education opportunities (Chell, 2014). Entrepreneurship has been considered as important force that boosts economic growth and creating Jobs (Haislip, 2011). There are a number of events which focus on entrepreneurship, for instance, the global entrepreneurship week which is celebrated around the world. The aim being to expose the benefits of entrepreneurship to people and encourages people to explore their business ideas and new ventures. Start up weekend is a non-profit organization with a global presence in over 100 countries which aims at promoting entrepreneurship networking in different parts of the world. During that time, a hour weekend is organized whereby people with different backgrounds come together as teams and work throughout the weekend on developing and exchanging business idea (Schramm, 2012). Many awards are frequently given to successful entrepreneurs, for instance the earnest and young entrepreneurs of the year awards which reach 50 countries worldwide. The global award for entrepreneurship research which was established in 1996 is also another very important event (Henrekson & Lundstrom, 2010). Since entrepreneurship is relevance to economic growth, social value as well as job creation it means more knowledge about entrepreneurship can therefore speed up the development of entrepreneurial activity for individual firms as well as the societies as a whole (Lohreke, 2010). The entrepreneurship concept is not limited to creating personal or shareholders value

with private business; it can also be about creating value for customers’ wealth, shareholders wealth as well as creating benefits for other stakeholders and the society at large (Hitt, 2011). On the other hand, social entrepreneurship which is a type of entrepreneurship aims at solving societal and consequently creating social value (Austin, 2006). It is due to the realization of the importance in contributing to economic growth that entrepreneurship education has become a popular topic in various universities.

The theory of Entrepreneurial Passion

The theory of entrepreneurial passion was advocated by Cardon (2009). The theory argues that once an entrepreneurial passion has been stimulated as a result an engagement in entrepreneurial activities, it results in an elaborate definite experience which involves an engagement of brain and body which can be expressed in appraisals and cognition and also physiological and behaviour responses (Russell, 2003). The theory advocates that the perception of the emotional experience recognizes that the brain and the body responses has been stimulated by passion does not act independently , but on the contrary it is articulated and is synchronized and sustained overtime (Damasio, 2001). It can therefore be argued that the experience of passion aids an entrepreneur’s effort in adapting environmental challenges. This theory is relevant in the study because it endeavored to investigate the students’ ability to cope with environmental dynamism as they create new ventures when they graduate

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a model of presentation. The researcher conceptualizes the existing relationships between variables under study, then shows the relationship either diagrammatically or graphically (Orotho, 2008). A conceptual framework is a hypothesized model identifying variables under study and showing their relationship Orotho (2008).

Conceptual Framework (E.E)

Teaching Methods

Popular teaching methods in entrepreneurship education are creation of business plan, case studies and lectures Solomon (2002). Many ways of delivering entrepreneurship education depends on the main objectives of the education (Hytti & O’ Gorman, 2004). If the objective of education is to increase the understanding of what entrepreneurship is all about, the effective way to accomplish that objective is the provision of information through public channels for example media, seminars as well as lectures sessions. The methods are effective since they will deliver message to a group of people within a short time period. If the objective on the other hand would be to equip individuals with entrepreneurial abilities, the preferred way would be to provide education in a form of training whereby the individuals are directly involved in the entrepreneurial process as it happens in an industrial training (Hytti& O’ Gorman, 2004). On the other hand, if the objective of the study was preparing students to act as entrepreneurs, the appropriate technique would be carrying out of experiments in a controlled area (Ahamed ., 2004).

Entrepreneurship teaching has been categorized into two “traditional methods” which is also referred to as normal methods and the “innovative methods’ also called the action based method. The two methods have as well been referred to as either passive or active methods of teaching (Mwaslwiba, 2010). The active method requires that the instructor facilitates learning and not to control and apply methods that would otherwise enable the students to have a self discovery during the learning session. In teaching entrepreneurship, the most commonly used methods are lecture methods, case study and group

discussion method. The same methods are also applied in teaching other business courses. They are passive and less effective in helping rifer an entrepreneurial intention among the learners

(Bennett, 2006). Fiet (2000), states that some instructors who rely on these methods do so because they are easier to accomplish and require less investment. Other methods applicable in teaching entrepreneurship include films and video, guest speakers, role model, preparation of a business plan, project works, games as well as competition, setting small ventures, workshops, presentations as well as study visits. These methods are active and more appropriate in inculcating an entrepreneurial propensity among students (Mwasalwiba, 2010). This study hypothesized that:

H01: *There is no significant relationship between teaching methods and entrepreneurial Propensity*

Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

The term ecosystem was first coined by James Moore in an influential article from Harvard Business Review that was published during the 1990s. James Moore argued that businesses do not exist in a vacuum. This is because the embedded nature firms interact with the customers, suppliers and even the financiers (Moore, 1993). Past studies have revealed that in a dynamic ecosystem, new firms have a better opportunity to grow and even create employment as opposed to firms created in other locations (Rosted, 2012).

Entrepreneurial ecosystem can be viewed as a set of interconnected entrepreneurial actors, either existing or has the potential to exist. Entrepreneurial organizations such as firms, financing institutions, universities as well as public sector agencies and entrepreneurial process such as start up enterprises and firms that are highly formal or informal connect, mediate and govern the performance within the local entrepreneurial environment Rosted, 2012). Several models of entrepreneurial ecosystem have been developed by different scholars. Daniel Isenberg of Babson College developed an ecosystem model. He articulated it and he referred to as an 'entrepreneurship ecosystem strategy for economic development (Isenberg, 2011). Daniel Isenberg argued that an approach like that claimed that such formed a novel, cost strategy for stipulating economic growth of any Nation. Such an approach becomes a pre-condition for successful entrepreneurial activities such as knowledge economy, innovation systems, as well as national competitiveness policies (Isenberg, 2013).

An entrepreneurial ecosystem basically comprises of six domains. The domains of an entrepreneurial ecosystem includes a conducive culture, enabling policies and leadership, availability of finance , quality human capital, venture markets that are and friendly and a range of institutional support (Isenberg, 2011). The above domains have elements which interact in a highly complicated and idiosyncratic ways (Isenberg, 2011). Each ecosystem emerges under a unique set of conditions and circumstances within which the ecosystems operates (Isenberg, 2011). An entrepreneurial ecosystem can be industry specific. It may evolve from a single industry to include other industries (Isenberg, 2013). They are also graphically bounded, yet again cannot be confined to one specific geographical location. Entrepreneurial ecosystems are also not related to one particular city (Isenberg, 2013).

Entrepreneurial ecosystem is a relevant variable in this study. The study sought to investigate the influence of the ecosystems in determining entrepreneurial propensity among students. Students come from diverse parts of the Country and merge in an institution. The ecosystems of where they come from are different and operate differently and can positively or negatively influence their rate of preparedness to become entrepreneurs upon graduation.

Environmental Dynamism and Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education has a great influence in inculcating an entrepreneurial propensity. A few studies have been carried out on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and environmental dynamism. Several factors have been identified as determinant of entrepreneurial propensity such as, self-efficacy, (Boyd & Vozikis, 1994; Mobaraki & Zane, 2012) Entrepreneurship education (Jorge & Merono et al., 2012; Solesvik, 2013). (Gupta & Turban, 2009; Wilson et al., 2007). Schwarz *et al.*, (2009) have called for studies on personal and environmental factors in determining entrepreneurial propensity. Paucity in entrepreneurial and especially at individual level is perturbing (Gupta, 2015). Suresh and Ramray (2012) suggest that an individual characteristic isn't enough to determine entrepreneurship propensity in an individual. Results in past studies have remained contradictory (Ahl. 2006; Hmielski & Corbett 2006) therefore the need for a moderating variable (Baron & Kenny, 1986). This study proposed environmental dynamism as a possible moderator, moderating the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial propensity.

Entrepreneurial Propensity

The term propensity refers to a personal disposition to act on one's decision. It is that inner push that propels an individual to act entrepreneurially. (Bateman & Crant, 1993; Krueger, 1993). Krueger (2000) argued that entrepreneurial propensity can be as a result of certain cultural values within a given environment such as availability of business opportunities. That the trigger can also be as a result of an individual possessing entrepreneurial traits, their ability to take responsibility as well as being personally motivated to act. Burns (2001) on the other hand proposes that for an individual to become an entrepreneur, probably it was in their characteristic traits, or the situation favourable presented itself or it could be as a result of the culture of the society within which an individual lives can also trigger the propensity to become an entrepreneur. Scholars and government officials have in the recent past shown a growing interest in business start up and especially those started by well educated individuals (European Commission, 2008). Such initiatives are viewed as paramount because past studies have shown that basic literacy in entrepreneurial concepts is bound to increase awareness on entrepreneurial career which students can choose to engage in upon graduation (Greene, 2010). Past studies have revealed that entrepreneurship can be learnt. It can therefore be argued that a well designed University programme can promote components that are necessary for entrepreneurship such as taking risk, independency and creativity among other elements (Gibb, 2002). Despite the efforts put in place, it has remained quiet unclear which factors actually influence an entrepreneurial propensity especially among students (Gartner, 2004). The cause for such uncertainty can be attributed to the differences in entrepreneurship education between countries or even across the same Country and one institution from another (Kuratko, 2005; Pittway and Cope, 2007). Since there isn't one fact concluded on what propels students toward entrepreneurship as a career option, it would be vital to combine both perspectives, focus on the individual analysis level and also explore the factors that students consider as leading him or her towards entrepreneurship within a University environment (Krueger and Brazeal, 1994).

Entrepreneurial propensity is the dependent variable that this study endeavored to investigate. The main question that this study endeavored to answer was what are the extrinsic and intrinsic factors that exert greater influence on the surveyed students towards entrepreneurship? Which are the factors that favour or prevent students from the sample taken considering entrepreneurship as a career option of choice? There exists a variety of 'pull' and 'push' factors that give an insight on students' propensity towards entrepreneurship (Boissin, 2009)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design. Description is the precise measurement and reporting of the attributes of some population or phenomenon that are under study (Rubin & Babbie, 2010). The awareness of the characteristic of a group which allows the ability to gauge the aspects of the situation, to provide information for further studies and assemble data around possible changes becomes its outcome (Cavana, Delahaye & Sekaran, 2001). A descriptive design has been used in this study to elaborate on the perspective of entrepreneurship education in as far as the literature review is concerned. It has also been used to determine the occurrence of the study through a survey method with use of questionnaires (Kinnear, 1993). However, the descriptive design does not establish a direct cause and effect relationship that exists between the variables under study. To address the cause and effect aspect, a causal design has been adopted to fulfil this purpose (Zikmund, 2003)

Population of the Study

The population of this study were University students who were in fourth year and pursuing entrepreneurship course at degree level. The selection of the students was advised by their enrolment in Entrepreneurship programme which provide an indication that their career interest is skewed toward business related field (Zainuddin & Ismail, 2011). The assumption is that they were likely to become entrepreneurs in future. The study population comprised of 607 students undertaking a degree in entrepreneurship in both private and public chartered universities in Kenya who are in the fourth year of study. Ibrahim, Bakar, Aimna & Zakana (2015) used a population of final year students of electrical technology in their study on the impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention in both technical and vocational training institution. Guyo, Golo & Dida (2010) used a population of final year undergraduates' students of business and economics from Addis Ababa University on a study on entrepreneurial intentions and its determinant: Evidence from University of Addis Ababa. Past studies have shown that graduates between the ages of 20 to 25 have a high tendency towards starting their own ventures.

Universities Offering Bachelors in Business Entrepreneurship.

Name of University	Number of Students (N)
Kenya Methodist University	68
Jomo Kenyatta University	55
Kisii University	50
Egerton University	140
Moi University	85
Meru University	55
Karatina University	39
Chuka	90
Kirinyag'a	25
TOTAL	607

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

A probability sampling was used for the study. Fayolle & Gailly (2008) suggested that such sampling is easy to use and has often been used in entrepreneurship research. Afriyie & Boohene used it to obtain the sample on a study about entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial culture among University students of cape coast. This study used a simple random sampling method. The sample should be sufficient enough to represent the entire population. Mugenda & Mugenda (2003) has recommended a 20-30% sample of a target population. The following statistical method was used to calculate the sample size for the study Zikmund, (2010).

Equation (1)

Where n = required sample size Z = Population size

p = population proportions (probability of acquiring an entrepreneurial

propensity) q = (1- p) probability of not acquiring an entrepreneurial propensity

E / 2 = is the allowable error or margin of error. $Z_{\alpha/2} = 0.95/2$ 0.475 Therefore Z-Score is 1.96

$E=1.5\% / 2 = 0.075$ $P=50\%$ $q=1-0.5 = 0.5$

Therefore: $p \times q$ $0.5 \times 0.5=0.25$

$Z/E = 1.96/0.075=26.13$ $26.13 \times 26.13=682.95$

$0.25 \times 682.95 = 180$

Maina & Kyalo (2017) used the same formula to get a sample for their study on examining the pedagogy of entrepreneurship education and its contribution in creating entrepreneurship in Kenya.

Sampling Procedure for the Population

Universities	No. students (N) Percentages %	Sample Size (n)
Kenya Methodist University	37%	25
Jomo Kenyatta University	27%	15
Kisii University	34%	17
Egerton University	21%	30
Moi University	29%	25
Meru University	36%	20
Karatina University	26%	10
Chuka University	33%	30
Kirinyaga University	32%	8
TARGET POPULATION (607)		SAMPLE SIZE: 180

Data Collection Instruments

A research instrument is used to measure the variables of the study (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2008). The choice of a primary data collection method depend on the purpose of the study, skills of the scholar, available resources, the socioeconomic-demographic as well as the characteristics of the study population Kumar (2005). This study used questionnaire with closed ended and open-ended questions. Questionnaires provide an efficient way of collecting responses from a large sample as the respondents will be responding to the same set of questions Lewis Thornhill (2009). Kothari (2009) explains that a questionnaire should consist of a number of questions that are printed or typed in a definite way on a form or set of forms. Semi-structured questions were an effective way of collecting information within a short span and also because they are less costly compared to other data collection methods (Cooper & Schindler, 2011).

They consisted of a series of specific short questions which are either closed or open ended (Bryman & Bell, 2011). The closed ended were useful in eliciting factual information. On the other hand, open ended questions sought opinions, attitudes and perceptions of the respondents (Kumar, 2005). Open-ended questionnaire allows the respondents the freedom to respond with any value, words, statements which are of their own choice. The structured questions were accompanied by a list of possible alternatives from which the respondents selected answers that would best described their specific institution (Groebner, Shannon, Fry & Smith, 2008). Closed ended items adopted a five likert scale since its more reliable and can give more information (Kothari, 2009). The scale ranged from 1 to 5 where 1 assumed strongly disagree and 5 a strongly agree scenario that the respondent is propelled towards entrepreneurship (Ida & Mahmood 2011).

Pilot Study

A pilot study was carried out before the actual data was collected. A Pilot study is normally the first phase in data gathering process. Its main purpose is to detect any weaknesses in the design and instrumentation so that alternative data can be selected from the probability sample (Cooper & Schindler, 2011). Pilot study measures the reliability and the validity of the research instruments (Kothari, 2008). Pilot testing is used to detect the weaknesses in the design and also in its implementation as well as providing proxy for data collection probability sample (Cooper & Schindler, 2008). Pilot study also provides proxy data for selection of a probability sample (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009).

Reliability of Data Collection Instrument

Reliability is the proportion of variance attributed to the measurement of variable. It estimates the consistency of measurements within a given period of time (Mugenda & Mugenda 2003). Reliability measures the degree which a research instrument is able to yield results that are consistent after data has been repeated and tried (Gall & Borg, 2007). It is the one that answers the question on whether the results found in a study can be duplicated (Bryman & Bell, 2011).

Cronbach alpha (α) was used to test the reliability of the instrument. It calculates the average of possible split-half reliability coefficient. A Cronbach alpha (α) was used in order to ensure that the items have a good internal consistency (Bryman, 2012). A computed alpha coefficient varies between 1 and 0. If it's 1, it explains that there's a perfect reliability where 0 denotes lack of reliability. If the coefficient is 0, the instrument is considered as unreliable. The greater the coefficient, the greater the accuracy and reliable an instrument's score is (Bryman & Bell, 2011). A Cronbach alpha that is 0.8 and above indicates a level of consistency that is reliable. Guyo, Golo & Dida (2013) used Cronbach alpha and obtained an alpha of 0.85 on their study on entrepreneurial intention and its determinants evidence from the University students from Addis Ababa Ethiopia.

Ethical Considerations

The study ensured integrity and that the dignity of the respondents was protected. To achieve this, prior to data collection, an approval letter was obtained. The researcher was allowed to collect data from the respondents by the National Association of Commission for science Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI). Besides that, the data collection tool was designed to be objective. The participants gave information voluntarily. No one was forced or coerced to answer any question(s). The researched data was secured throughout the research period and no individual information provided was divulged to any other party in order to ensure confidentiality. Upon the completion of data collection, the data collected was treated with confidentiality to ensure that all privacy of the respondents was maintained.

The findings of the study were reported accurately and represented what was provided and the results were not presented in a way which would take the findings out of context, deceive readers, exaggerate claims or focus on smaller parts of the observation and failing to put them into perspective.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

Descriptive Analysis of Entrepreneurship Teaching Method

The first objective of the study was to establish the role of entrepreneurship teaching method in inculcating entrepreneurial propensity among the students. Mwaslwiba, (2010) points out two methods that have been used to teach entrepreneurship, that is, a traditional method and an innovative method. The traditional method is passive and innovative. It is action based and entrepreneurial in nature. To achieve this objective, respondents were asked to identify items that are related to teaching and had played a role in propelling them towards entrepreneurship as a career choice.

In their response, majority (53%) indicated that the method used to teach entrepreneurship was theoretical while few (45 %) indicated that the instructors used practical and theoretical method in their teaching as shown in Table 4.8. The key to successful entrepreneurship education is to find the effective way to manage the teachable skills and identify best match between students’ needs and teaching techniques (Lee, 2007). Hytti and O’Gorman (2004) suggest that the way entrepreneurship is taught depends on the objective of the education. If the objective is to equip individuals with entrepreneurship skills, that are applicable to work, then the best method would be to offer education and training. If the objective is to prepare the individual to act as an entrepreneur, the effective method is to facilitate experiments by trying entrepreneurship out in a controlled environment (innovative method).

Since one key objective of any University which has taken entrepreneurship education seriously is to enable students practice entrepreneurship, it is important to consider innovative method of teaching entrepreneurship as opposed to traditional method. An innovative method will enable students to start up businesses while in the University or upon graduation. This also means that, innovative method leads to an entrepreneurial attitude and ignites an entrepreneurial passion irrespective of the environmental dynamism. In today’s world, any firm that does not innovative dies. It is forced out of the market by the firms that are willing to adopt to new technologies and new methods of business operations hence being innovative is very key in ensuring business success.

Model fits Between Teaching Methods and Entrepreneurial Propensity

Measure	NFI	SRMR	RMS-Theta
Estimate	0.967	0.058	0.057
Threshold	>0.90	<0.08	<0.12
Interpretation	Good fit	Good fit	Good fit

NFI: >0.90 SRMR<0.08 RMS <0.12

The Structural model fitted showed that the three measures of the observed indicators (Method of delivery, idea generation and innovation load highly the independent variable (Teaching methods). The observed parameters (Desirability, Feasibility and self-efficacy) of the dependent variable were found to load highly on entrepreneurial propensity. Teaching methods was found to have a positive relationship with entrepreneurial propensity with the path coefficient of teaching method and entrepreneurial propensity being 0.628.

Regression Weights for Teaching Methods on Entrepreneurial propensity

Path	Beta	Sample Mean	Standard Error	T Statistics	P values
Propensity -> Desirability	0.752	0.755	0.040	8.9791	0.000
Propensity -> Feasibility	0.869	0.868	0.020	42.619	0.000
Propensity -> Self Efficacy	0.890	0.891	0.024	36.976	0.000
Teaching Methods -> BIG	0.859	0.861	0.021	40.443	0.000
Teaching Methods -> INN	0.710	0.709	0.048	14.718	0.000
Teaching Methods -> MD	0.894	0.894	0.017	52.731	0.000
Teaching Methods -> Propensity	0.628	0.627	0.057	11.125	0.000

This study found that teaching method is statistically significant ($t=11.125$ and $p=0.000$). From the results in the study, it can be deduced that the proportion of variance in entrepreneurial propensity that is accounted for by teaching methods is substantial. The question on whether entrepreneurship should be taught and whether entrepreneurs are born has been ongoing. However, there is a general opinion that entrepreneurs can be trained and hence students acquire an entrepreneurial propensity from a classroom setting (Solomon & Frenald, 1991). Rae & Carswell (2001) in their study there is a difference between teachable and non teachable methods applied to teach entrepreneurship. Lee (2007) states that the key elements to successful entrepreneurship education is to find the effective way that can be applied in order to manage the teachable method and match those methods to the students needs. The methods used to teach entrepreneurship has been referred as both an art and a science (Jack & Anderson, 1995).

Regression Weights for Teaching Methods on Entrepreneurial propensity

Path	Beta Sample	Mean Standard	Error	T Statistics	P values
Propensity -> Desirability	0.752	0.755	0.040	18.979	0.000
Propensity -> Feasibility	0.868	0.869	0.020	42.619	0.000
Propensity -> Self Efficacy	0.890	0.891	0.024	36.976	0.000
Teaching Methods -> BIG	0.859	0.861	0.021	40.443	0.000
Teaching Methods -> INN	0.710	0.709	0.048	14.718	0.000
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Significance Test Results of Teaching Methods Moderated effect of Entrepreneurship Education on the Relationship between Teaching Methods and Entrepreneurial Propensity among University Students in Kenya

The moderating effect of environmental dynamism was determined by introducing an interaction variable (Teaching method* Environmental Dynamism) in the model and testing of the new model and the significance of the parameters in the model. The fitness indices of the moderated model met both the absolute fitness and incremental fitness requirements. The results of the fitness indices for the moderated effect on the relationship between environmental dynamism and entrepreneurial propensity are represented in Table 4.42. The model fits was assessed using SRMR, NFI and RMS theta as recommended by

Hair et al (2010). The values for NFI after moderation was 0.902 against a threshold of >0.902 meaning the model had an incremental effect on the selected data hence the model was fit. The SRMR value was 0.077 against a threshold of <0.08 and RMS theta was 0.041 measured against a threshold of <0.12 respectively meaning the model was fit for the test

Measure	NFI	SRMR	RMS_theta
Estimate	0.902	0.077	0.041
Threshold	>0.90	<0.08	<0.12
Interpretation	Good fit	Good fit	Good fit

Model Fits for the Moderated Model for Teaching Methods

The model including the moderating variable environmental dynamism and the interaction variable (Teaching Method interaction Environmental Dynamism) was found to be significant with all factors having significant effect on entrepreneurial propensity. On this moderated influence, the interaction variable was found to be significant implying that

environmental dynamism has a significant effect on the relationship between teaching method and entrepreneurial propensity. The path coefficient used for moderating (ED) that is $TM * ED$ was 6.1412 and significant at 0.05 level. This indicates that the moderator (ED) has a positive relationship with teaching method. Figure 4.3 shows the path diagram of the structural equation model. The test of significance was done by assessing the significance of the ratio between 0.05 levels of significance. The moderated interaction term was 1.0073 which is greater than 0.05 hence significant at 0.05 levels of significance. It means therefore that ED moderates the relationship between teaching method and entrepreneurial propensity among University students in Kenya.

The test on whether environmental dynamism moderates teaching method was performed by introducing the interaction term Teaching* Dynamism as a predictor alongside teaching methods and environmental dynamism. The two variables (teaching method) and environmental dynamism had positive regression weights of $t = 6.1412$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$ meaning the values obtained in the model were within the threshold as shown in The interaction term was negative ($\beta = -0.3654$). This means when teaching method is interacted with the moderator it results to negative influence to entrepreneurial propensity. When one unit of teaching methods is increased, and moderated by environmental dynamism, entrepreneurial propensity among students decreases by 37%. This means the moderator had negative effect on the relationship between teaching methods and entrepreneurial propensity.

Teaching* Dynamism revealed a significant effect of environmental dynamism on the relationship between teaching methods and entrepreneurial propensity hence the study concluded that environmental dynamism negatively moderates the relationship between teaching methods and entrepreneurial propensity. Milliken (1987) considered environmental dynamism as speed of product changes, the changing frequency of customer preference and operational environment. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of TM when interjected with a moderating variable (ED) was 0.109 or 11% change. This means the change caused by TM latent variable (teaching method) after ED has been introduced is only 11%. Environmental dynamism are destructive in nature. They move people from their comfort zone and naturally demand for change. Since human beings are naturally change averse, the respondents could have felt that they could not comfortably embrace the dynamic changes within the environment which actually cause a lot of uncertainties hence the moderator had a negative effect on entrepreneurial propensity. Although not much has been studied on teaching method moderated by environmental dynamism, this study adds to the body of knowledge on the negative effect caused by a moderator (environmental dynamism).

Regression Weights for the Moderated Teaching Methods Model

Path	Beta	Standard Error	T Statistics	P values
Dynamism -> Propensity	0.0898	0.0891	1.0073	0.315
Teaching*Dynamism -> Propensity	-0.3654	0.0595	6.1412	0.000
Teaching Methods -> Propensity	0.4482	0.0654	6.8516	0.000

P values: 0.315 > 0.05, 0.000 > 0.05

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Influence of Teaching Method and Entrepreneurial Propensity

Teaching methods had a relationship with entrepreneurial propensity among University students in Kenya. Three factors which are delivery method, idea generation and innovativeness contributed to the teaching methods which influenced entrepreneurial propensity. Hence the hypothesis that there is no relationship between teaching methods and entrepreneurial propensity among University students was rejected. Teaching method and entrepreneurial propensity had a statistical significant relationship with entrepreneurial propensity among University students in Kenya. A study carried out by Ahamed (2004) suggests that if the objective of the study is to make students entrepreneurs, then the appropriate technique that can be used is carrying out experiments. The same thought is advanced in the experimental learning theory adopted in this study.

Since the objective of introducing entrepreneurship education in Kenya was to encourage an entrepreneurial culture among Kenyan students, it can be summarized that use of innovative methods and idea generation still remains vital in inculcating entrepreneurial propensity as supported in this study.

Conclusion

The results on teaching methods revealed that an effective teaching method of entrepreneurship can facilitate an increase in students' interest towards considering entrepreneurship as a career option as was also noted by Gelard and Saleh (2011). This is possible to attain because entrepreneurship education can equip the learner with the required knowledge and skills effectively. The entrepreneurship education process can effectively advice the students on how to tackle challenging situations and the complexities involved in decision making in considering entrepreneurship as a career option among entrepreneurship students (Izquierdo and Buelens, 2011). During the learning process the perception and the impediments that are related with entrepreneurship as a career option can be downplayed and consequently students may be motivated to create their own ventures and establish their business start –ups (Ahmad, 2010)

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